

Antibacterial Potential Of Iron Oxide Nanoparticles In Uropathogens

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ABSTRACT: The treatment of infectious diseases caused by bacteria has become problematic due to antibiotic resistance in bacteria. The major cause of antibiotic resistance is the irrational use of antibiotics. Antibiotic resistance is common in urinary tract bacteria. Therefore, the development of alternative approaches to combat antibiotic resistance is needed. Advancement in green nanotechnology offers a great opportunity to limit the antibiotic resistance in microbes. Different nanomaterial-based antimicrobial agents, like nano-emulsions, have been traditionally used for the treatment of microbial infections. Nanotechnology has important role in treatment of urinary tract infections (UTIs) and made significant advancement in the treatment of UTIs by the use of metallic nanoparticles. Due to the antimicrobial properties of metallic nanoparticles, they can limit the growth of bacteria, allowing to overcome the multidrug resistance (MDR) and reduction in formation of biofilms through targeted drug delivery to the sites of infection. This study was planned to demonstrate the incidence of antibiotic resistance in uropathogens, which were isolated from urine of UTIs patients. In this study, antibacterial potential of iron oxide nanoparticles against uropathogens (*Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*) was assessed. Sapodilla leaves were used for green synthesis of iron oxide nanoparticles. Sapodilla leave extract could reduce iron to iron oxide. A total 40 urine samples were collected from urology ward of Nishtar Hospital Multan, Punjab for culturing purpose. The samples were analyzed by disc diffusion and well diffusion methods. The growth of bacterial strains which shows resistance against antibiotics were limited by using colloidal iron oxide NPs ug/mL (40-80uL). Results suggested that iron oxide nanoparticles have antibacterial potential.

Keywords: Infectious diseases, Antibiotic resistance, UTIs, Nanotechnology, Iron oxide nanoparticles